

complexes have been tentatively assigned from the colour similarities of these complexes with that of *trans*-diaquobismalonato-⁶ and *trans*-diaquobismethylmalonato-⁶ complexes.

Molar conductances in aqueous solution of the complexes indicated that the *tris*-complexes were tri-univalent in nature while the diaquobis-complexes were uni-univalent in nature. Molar conductance values of all the complexes are also given in Table I.

The electronic spectra of all these complexes showed two bands. The lower energy band may be assigned to the transition ${}^4A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}$ and the higher energy band to ${}^4T_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}$ transition. Both the bands were well defined but the extinctions were usually small.

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Complexes of Some Bivalent Metals with 4-Amino-5-Oxo-3-Thioxo-6-Benzyl-2,3,4,5-Tetrahydro-1,2,4-Triazine and Its Derivatives

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Manuscript received 11 November 1980, revised 23 July 1981, accepted 11 August 1981

4-Amino-5-oxo-3-thioxo-6-benzyl-2,3,4,5-tetrahydro-1,2,4-triazine (BTH) and its 6-*o*-chlorobenzyl (CBTH) and 6-*p*-methoxybenzyl (MBTH) derivatives (shown below) are multidentate

(X = benzyl, *o*-chlorobenzyl or *p*-methoxybenzyl)

ligands but their complexes with metal ions are not known. In present communication the preparation and characterisation of complexes of these ligands with Ni(II), Co(II), Cu(II), Zn(II) and Cd(II) are reported.

Experimental

BTH, CBTH and MBTH were prepared by method of Dornov¹ and uv, ir and magnetic susceptibilities were measured as reported earlier².

Preparation of complexes; ML_2 ($M = \text{Co}^{2+}$, Ni^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , or Cd^{2+} and $LH = \text{BTH}$, MBTH or CBTH): A methanolic solution of hydrated metal(II) chloride (acetate in case of Cd^{2+} and Zn^{2+}) was added with stirring to the ligand dissolved in hot methanol (1:2 metal to ligand molar ratio) containing 6–7 g of sodium acetate. The resulting solution was refluxed on a steam bath for about 20–30 mins and diluted with an excess of water when neutral *bis* chelate separated out as a flocculent precipitate. In some cases the complex separated immediately on mixing the reactants. The products were filtered, washed with water and methanol and dried at 120°.

$\text{Ni}(\text{MBT})_2$; (Orange-red form): Methanolic solution of hydrated Ni(II) chloride was refluxed with stoichiometric proportion of the ligand dissolved in pyridine-dioxane mixture. The resulting solid product was removed and the filtrate was diluted with excess of water when a flocculent orange-red product separated.

$\text{Ni}(\text{LH})_2\text{Cl}_2$; ($LH = \text{BTH}$ and MBTH): Stoichiometric proportion of the ligand was suspended in methanolic solution of hydrated nickel(II) chloride (1.2 g in 100 ml) and refluxed on a steam bath for about 1 hr. The resulting solution was concentrated to a small volume and the complex was separated by adding excess of ether. The product was filtered and washed thoroughly with ether and dried in a desiccator over CaCl_2 .

$\text{Cu}(\text{LH})\text{Cl}_2 \cdot \text{CH}_3\text{OH}$; ($LH = \text{BTH}$, CBTH and MBTH); $\text{Cu}(\text{BTH})\text{Br}_2 \cdot Y$; ($Y = \text{CH}_3\text{OH}$ or $\text{C}_4\text{H}_8\text{O}_2$) and $\text{Cu}(\text{BTH})\text{Cl}_2 \cdot \text{C}_4\text{H}_8\text{O}_2$: Stoichiometric proportion of methanolic solution of appropriate cupric halide (0.005 mole) was added to the ligand dissolved in hot methanol with stirring. On cooling the resulting solution, solvated complex separated as a fine crystalline product. The product was filtered washed with methanol and dried in air. The dioxane solvated complex was obtained when the preparation was carried out in dioxane-methanol mixture.

Results and Discussion

In alkaline medium these ligands are deprotonated and form inner bischelates and analytical results of the dried samples correspond with the formula $[\text{ML}_2]$ [$M = \text{Co}(\text{II})$, $\text{Ni}(\text{II})$, $\text{Cu}(\text{II})$, $\text{Zn}(\text{II})$ or $\text{Cd}(\text{II})$ and $LH = \text{BTH}$, MBTH or CBTH]. The analytical results of dihalo complexes $\text{Cu}(\text{LH})\text{X}_2 \cdot Z$ [$X = \text{Cl}$ or Br and $Z = \text{CH}_3\text{OH}$ or dioxane] and $\text{Ni}(\text{LH})_2\text{Cl}_2$ [$LH = \text{BTH}$ or MBTH] are also in good agreement of the suggested formulae. The methanolic solutions of dihalo complexes $\text{Ni}(\text{LH})_2\text{Cl}_2$ and $\text{Cu}(\text{LH})\text{X}_2 \cdot Z$ display negligible conductance value (Λ_m 10–20 $\text{ohm}^{-1}\text{mol}^{-1}\text{cm}^2$) indicating that halogen atoms are coordinated to metal atom in these complexes.

As usual Zn(II) and Cd(II) complexes are diamagnetic and do not display electronic reflectance band in the visible region. Excepting $\text{Cu}(\text{BT})_2$ which is diamagnetic, other inner bischelates of copper(II)

display subnormal magnetic moment values at room temperature. The magnetic moment values of dihalo complexes (1.77–1.91 BM) indicate that they are magnetically dilute³⁻⁶. In case of inner bischelates CuL_2 , the subnormal magnetic moment values of the complexes can be attributed to spin-spin interaction by the overlap of d_{z^2} or $d_{x^2-y^2}$ orbitals between two Cu(II) atoms and this interaction in case of $\text{Cu}(\text{BT})_2$ is so strong that paramagnetism associated with cupric ion is completely quenched⁴⁻⁶. In case of bulky ligand molecules like MBTH and CBTH this interaction is rather less and therefore partial quenching is observed in their inner complexes⁶.

Inner bischelates of Ni(II) also display anomalous magnetic moment values at room temperature ($\mu_{\text{eff}} = 1.51 - 2.69$ BM) attributable to the presence of varying proportion of 6-coordinated distorted octahedral species along with planar nickel(II) species^{7,9}. The magnetic moment values of Co(II) complexes ($\mu_{\text{eff}} = 2.01 - 2.76$ BM) are similar to square planar or spin-paired octahedral complexes⁹. The magnetic moment values of $\text{Ni}(\text{LH})_2\text{Cl}_2$ [LH=BTH or MBTH] fall between 2.89 BM and 3.38 BM which are in the range of octahedral nickel(II) complexes^{10,11}.

The reflectance spectra of CoL_2 [LH=BTH or MBTH] display two weak bands or shoulders at 16130–18520 cm^{-1} and 21740–22570 cm^{-1} assignable to d-d transitions⁹. The dihalo as well as neutral copper(II) complexes CuL_2 display a broad and asymmetric band in the region 12500–13500 cm^{-1} attributable to the combination of ${}^2\text{B}_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2\text{A}_{1g} + {}^2\text{B}_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2\text{B}_{2g}$ transitions in distorted octahedral field¹²⁻¹⁴. The strong absorption at 24500–25320 cm^{-1} in $\text{Cu}(\text{BT})_2$ and $\text{Cu}(\text{LH})\text{Cl}_2 \cdot \text{CH}_3\text{OH}$ can be attributed to charge transfer plus some contribution of ${}^2\text{B}_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2\text{E}_g$ transition. Dihalonickel(II) complexes display three weak or medium bands at 11350–11430, ~15750 and 24390–26520 cm^{-1} assignable to transitions¹⁵ ${}^3\text{A}_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3\text{T}_{2g}(\text{F})$, $\rightarrow {}^3\text{T}_{1g}(\text{F})$ and $\rightarrow {}^3\text{T}_{1g}(\text{P})$ respectively. The neutral bischelate $\text{Ni}(\text{BT})_2$ displays d-d transitions at 10750, 15380 and 24040 cm^{-1} as a shoulder or a very weak band. In case of the orange red complex $\text{Ni}(\text{MBT})_2$ the d-d transitions are observed at 10530, 20000, 22570 and 24570 cm^{-1} . The band at 22570 cm^{-1} can be attributed to ${}^1\text{A}_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1\text{B}_{1g}$ transition from the planar nickel(II) species in the complex¹⁶.

The ligands display a number of bands around 3μ region due to $\nu(\text{NH}_2)$, $\nu(\text{NH})$, $\nu(\text{CH}_2)$ and phenyl ring $\nu(\text{C-H})$ stretching vibrations (BTH, 3260m, 3170m, 3058m, 2998, 2884 and in CBTH at 3300m, 3210m, 3080m, 3015m and 2900w cm^{-1}). In some complexes, these bands between 3300–3000 cm^{-1} are affected appreciably in intensity and position but from this it is difficult to suggest the nature of bonding and deprotonation of the ligands.

The $\nu(\text{C=O})$ vibration of the free ligands (in BTH, 1676; CBTH, 1660 cm^{-1}) is shifted to higher wave number in their complexes by 10–40 cm^{-1} indicating that the oxo-oxygen is not involved in coordination.

The $\delta(\text{NH}_2)$ and $\beta(\text{NH}_2)$ of free ligands (BTH, 1600 and 1230 cm^{-1} , CBTH, 1584 and 1215 cm^{-1}) are shifted to higher frequencies in their complexes

which suggests that NH_2 nitrogen is involved in coordination with metal atoms¹⁷.

The thioamide bands (I to III)^{18,19} of the ligands (BTH, 1550vs, 1319m, 1065m cm^{-1} and of CBTH at 1540s, 1315m and 1070m cm^{-1}) are shifted to higher frequencies in complexes, indicative of bonding from thioxo sulphur of the ligand molecules. The thioamide band IV of BTH located at 888 cm^{-1} and of CBTH at 890 cm^{-1} is shifted to lower frequency by 155–200 cm^{-1} in neutral chelates indicating the bonding of thioxo sulphur by deprotonation of thiol form of the ligands. It is thus inferred that amino nitrogen and thioxo sulphur are the bonding sites of the ligand molecules in almost all the complexes.

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Alkali Metal Complexes: Adducts of Alkali Metal Salts of 1-Nitroso-2-Naphthol with Thiourea

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Manuscript received 30 May 1981, accepted 22 July 1981

TO unravel the mechanism of active transportation and storage of alkali metals from soil to plants in aqueous media, we have prepared some adducts of alkali metals with sulphur containing ligand in aqueous medium. Earlier Banerjee *et al.*^{1,2} prepared a number of similar adducts with oxygen and nitrogen containing ligands.